

Correspondence

Title: Logical paradoxes and epidemiological inconsistencies in vaccine-related vitiligo risk assessment

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To the Editor:

We wish to highlight critical methodological inconsistencies in the study published in *JACI* by Kim et al. [1]. Our analysis published in [2] demonstrates that the reported Hazard Ratio (HR) of 2.714 for Vitiligo is a statistical artifact. The study is trapped in two logical dead ends, depending on the temporal interpretation of the reported incidence.

Scenario A: The Annualized Interpretation If the observed incidence rate of 0.67 per 10,000 in the Non-Vaccinated (NV) group is taken as an annualized figure, it represents a deficit of over 70% compared to the established South Korean national baseline of 2.473 per 10,000 [3]. When this flawed denominator is corrected to account for the age difference between cohorts, the risk signal collapses to an HR of approximately 1, annulling any association with vaccination [2].

Scenario B: The Quarterly Interpretation If the 0.67 figure was intended as a quarterly rate, reconciliation with national epidemiology [3] leads to a biological impossibility. The annual South Korean incidence for the <20 age bracket unexplainably excluded from the original study was 3.4241 in 2019 according to [3]. Given that this group represents ~15% of the total population, its weighted contribution to the national baseline is approximately 0.5136. Annualizing the quarterly rates reported by Kim et al. [1], the Vaccinated group reaches an incidence of 8.88. By reintegrating the real-world contribution of the younger stratum (0.5136), the projected national incidence would be circa 9.4 per 10,000. This figure (9.4) is nearly 4 times higher than the verified national average of 2.473 [3]. Such a discrepancy describes a non-existent vitiligo epidemic that contradicts all available clinical registries.

In closing, both scenarios confirm that the original study lacks internal and external validity, in contrast with the STROBE protocol as well. The fact that these flawed data have been circulating for over eighteen months, thus becoming sedimented errors, does not diminish the need for correction; on the contrary, it exacerbates the risk. Misleading

information, when allowed to remain forever in the literature, risks being crystallized as clinical fact, potentially misguiding future research and public health policies.

We invite the authors to clarify how these disproportionate rates can be reconciled with the South Korean clinical reality. Furthermore, we ask the Editor to take immediate measures to restore scientific and epidemiological truth, ensuring that readers are not misled by these unsustainable risk estimates.

References

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STATEMENTS

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The Author declares no use of AI: he wrote and reviewed the manuscript as needed and takes full responsibility for the scientific integrity of the mathematical calculations and the final content of the publication.